

EFFECTS OF VARYING FIBRE VOLUME FRACTION IN SELECTIVELY REINFORCED Ti - 6Al - 4V MATRIX ALLOY COMPOSITES.

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ABSTRACT

Ti - 6Al - 4V plates have been selectively reinforced with SiC fibres in their central regions leaving monolithic layers of cladding on each side. Two volume fractions of reinforcement, 15.9 and 31% have been assessed. The fatigue crack growth resistance of these materials in the presence of an unbridged defect at room temperature has been investigated. For both volume fractions mode I fatigue cracks grow from single edged notches in the monolithic region. This crack grows towards the fibre reinforced region. Volume fraction has little effect on fatigue crack growth rates within the monolithic material. However, fatigue crack growth rates in the cladding regions were slightly faster than would have been predicted from monolithic data on Ti - 6 - 4 alloys. This is believed to be due to the effect of tensile residual stress in the cladding regions. In the composite region examples of mode I cracks, fibre bridging, crack bifurcation, and delamination have all been observed. Delamination appears to occur more readily in material reinforced with a volume fraction of 31% fibre.

INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced titanium MMCs show great promise for use as aerospace materials due to their high stiffness-to-weight ratios, and elevated temperature performance. Though currently limited by upper operating temperatures, realistic predictions indicate that these materials could replace current titanium and other alloys in a number of load bearing gas turbine components. Their high development and manufacturing costs would then be justified by considerably enhanced component properties and subsequently increased efficiencies. It would, however, be unrealistic to expect any final component to be made entirely of MMC, not only due to economic considerations, but also from a practical point of view. It is more probable that components would be selectively reinforced, and only in regions where greater stiffness and strength are required. In practice a monolithic layer would facilitate the joining of components and aid assembly. In these components fatigue cracks might be liable to initiate in the monolithic layer before growing through to the reinforced region.

To investigate such fatigue crack growth this study has made use of selectively reinforced unidirectional 8 ply Ti 6Al-4V/Sigma composite sheets, clad both top and bottom with a monolithic matrix layer. Two such composites were used, of nominal fibre volume fractions of 15.9% and 31.0%. To date the material costs of titanium MMCs, and the pressure to produce components, has meant that fundamental studies at relatively low volume fractions have not yet been pursued in detail.

EXPERIMENTAL

The materials used in this study were plates of Ti - 6Al - 4V (wt%), the central regions of which were reinforced with unidirectional 8 ply Sigma (SM1240) SiC fibres. These fibres have a tungsten core and a diameter of approximately 100 μm . The material was manufactured by DRA Composites and was produced from a lay-up of foils of Ti - 6Al - 4V and mats of SiC fibres where required. The material was consolidated in a single stage by HIPing at an approximate temperature of 910° C for 2 hours. Reinforced regions with nominal volume fractions of 15.9% and 31% were produced.

Test pieces were machined from the as received plates using electro-discharge-machining (EDM). The overall test piece dimensions for the 15.9 and 31% fibre reinforced composites were approximately 4.85 x 2.0 x 76 mm³ and 4.2 x 1.85 x 75 mm³ respectively. In both cases a single edge, through thickness notch, approximately 1 mm deep, was cut into one of the clad surfaces using a slow speed diamond wheel. Notches were cut such that the root of the notch did not extend into the reinforced region. The composites were loaded in three point bending using a total loading span of 60 mm. An Instron servo-hydraulic testing machine, fitted with a 10 kN load cell, was used to perform the fatigue tests. A cyclic frequency of 10Hz was used, with a variety of different load ranges and a R ratio of 0.1 (where $R = P_{\text{min}}/P_{\text{max}}$, and P_{min} , P_{max} are the minimum and maximum loads applied during the fatigue cycle respectively). All tests were performed at room temperature. Fatigue crack propagation was monitored by means of a direct current potential difference (DCPD) technique [1]. In all tests the fatigue crack was allowed to extend until it had grown beyond the monolithic cladding layer.

After testing specimens were examined optically to observe fatigue crack growth paths as the crack approached the reinforced region and also the nature of the fatigue damage in the fibre reinforced region. Fractographic examination of fatigue surfaces was accomplished by means of an Hitachi S4000 field emission gun (FEG) SEM, operating at 20kV.

Surface residual stresses in the *cladding layers* of the 15.9 and 31% fibre reinforced composite materials, have been analysed using the hole drilling strain gauge technique [2]. A high speed air turbine drill was used to drill a hole in the cladding layer. The hole depth is increased incrementally, by 0.0508 mm each time. The diameter of the hole was approximately 1.7 mm. (This limits the depth of the hole that can be drilled and analysed to approximately 1.2 mm for the present configuration of strain gauges). The micro strains measured from the triple rosette strain gauge (supplied by Measurements Group Inc, designated TEA-06-062RK-120) were processed [2] using micro computing facilities to produce residual stresses analysed over each total depth increment of drilling.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Optical micrographs of the transverse cross section of the material reinforced with 15.9% volume fraction of SiC fibres is shown in fig 1. The material can be seen to comprise of a central region reinforced with SiC fibres and unreinforced layers of cladding on both sides. The composite region is reinforced with eight mats of fibres. The material containing 31% volume fraction of SiC fibres has a similar cross section and the composite region also contains eight mats of fibres. In the material reinforced with 15.9% volume fraction of fibres the composite region is approximately 1.78 mm thick and the cladding layers are each approximately 1.53 mm thick. In the material containing 31% fibres the composite region is approximately 1.24 mm thick and the cladding layers are 1.48 mm thick. There is a smaller centre to centre inter fibre spacing within the mats in the material containing 31% volume fraction of fibres, (approximately 180 μm) than in that reinforced with 15.9% fibres (approximately 250 μm). The centre to centre fibre spacing between the mats is approximately 240 μm in the material reinforced with 15.9% fibres and approximately 160 μm in that containing 31% volume fraction of fibres.

Residual stresses measured parallel to the fibre direction in the cladding layers of the two different volume fraction materials are shown in fig 2. They are plotted against the incremental increases in hole depth, thus giving a stress profile within the cladding layer. The results exhibit a high degree of scatter up to a depth of 0.5 mm, probably because the small micro strains measured to determine the stresses are subject to more acute errors in measurement in the initial stages of drilling.

Tensile stresses arise in the cladding layer of selectively reinforced composites as a result of the mismatch in the coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) between the titanium matrix and the SiC fibres. The CTE of Ti - 6Al - 4V is greater than the effective CTE of the composite regions. Consequently on cooling, the titanium cladding will try to contract more than the composite region. The geometry of these composites is such that the composite section will be placed under net longitudinal stresses and the monolithic layers will be placed under net longitudinal tensile stresses.

Beyond a depth of 0.6 mm it is possible to see consistently higher residual stresses in the material containing 31% fibres than in that containing 15.9% fibres. The average residual stresses in the fibre direction are 118 MPa for material containing 15.9% fibres and 149 MPa for that reinforced with 31% fibres. This trend is further supported by work on similar material with a volume fraction of fibre reinforcement of 35%, where the residual stress parallel to the fibre direction has been found to be 195 MPa [1]. The indication is therefore, that the residual stresses in the cladding layer will increase with increasing volume fraction. This is also consistent with FE modelling predictions [3].

It should be noted that the thicknesses of the monolithic layers of the two materials are not identical, therefore any direct comparison of their residual stress measurements must be made with care. Of particular interest is the effect of cladding thickness, which may prove to produce considerable variations in residual stress [1, 3]. These effects are to be investigated in future work.

The stress profiles for both materials show that increases in residual stresses become less severe with increasing depth. This is further supported by other work on similar materials [1]. This suggests that beyond a certain depth the residual stresses in the cladding layers are more uniform. This is consistent with FEM predictions [3] However, measurements cannot be taken to the full depth of the cladding layer, as the hole drilling technique becomes insensitive at hole depths greater than approximately 0.7 times the hole diameter [2].

Fig 3 shows fatigue crack growth resistance curves through the cladding layer, in terms of da/dN versus ΔK . In considering the data, several points should be noted. Crack growth was monitored by means of the (DCPD) technique. The calibration used for such analysis [4] assumes that the entire specimen is uniform, not selectively reinforced. Consequently, adjustments must be made to the analysis, to allow for the fact that the total conducting area in the specimens will be greater than that of an entirely composite test piece of exactly the same geometry [1]. Additionally the DCPD calibration assumes that all crack growth is in the form a single mode I crack. This has been observed to be the case for crack growth in the cladding (see fig 4), but is not the case in the composite region, as described below. For the purposes of interpreting fig 3, once the crack reaches the first row of fibres, the data can no longer be considered valid. A reduction in da/dN may imply the phenomenon of fibre bridging, but it may be the result of sudden delamination and / or gradual mode II crack growth along fibre - matrix interfaces. The arrows on the plot and the stress intensities attached to each legend indicate the limit of DCPD validity. In addition it is possible that damage may be occurring in the composite region before the mode I crack reaches the fibres [1]. Such damage may also affect the DCPD values, hence the arrows in fig 3 indicate the absolute limits of the data validity. (Note each arrow is specific to the individual specimen under test).

DCPD data elsewhere are considered alongside corresponding measurements of surface replicas [1]. This work indicates that DCPD and replica measurements of crack growth are similar for mode I growth within the cladding layer. Hence, it is therefore considered that use of this technique is suitable for monitoring crack growth rates in the monolithic layer here.

It can be seen in fig 3 that there appears to be little difference in fatigue crack growth rates in the cladding layers of materials reinforced with 15.9 or 31% volume fraction of fibres. Also shown in fig 3 is data for the monolithic Ti - 6Al - 4V alloy, produced by a similar foil technique, and tested at a R ratio of 0.1 [5, 6]. The crack growth data through the cladding, in all the tests carried out at R = 0.1, tends to lie slightly above that of the monolithic data. (Initial crack growth rates are unusually low and may be disregarded here, as initiation and early growth occurs from a blunted notch rather than from a sharp crack.) It can be seen that the effect of residual stress on the fatigue crack growth rates in the cladding layer is to raise the effective mean stress. It is therefore not surprising that the data lies above that for foil produced monolithic Ti-6Al-4V, but the data does fall within the band given by high mean stress data for Ti-6Al-4V processed conventionally [7 - 9]. The effect of R ratio on the fatigue crack growth rates in this particular alloy are not marked [7]. Therefore, it is not unreasonable to expect crack growth rates for the materials reinforced with 15.9 and 31% volume fraction of fibres to be similar despite the difference in residual stress state (fig 2). Results are therefore consistent with the accepted view that the influence of residual stress is to increase the overall level of mean stress, but not to alter the stress intensity factor range.

After the crack reaches the fibres fig 3 indicates that the fatigue crack growth rates appear to decrease. This is most marked in the material containing 15.9% volume fraction of fibres. However, great caution must be exercised in interpreting this data because the crack growth mechanisms in this region are highly complex (see figs.4 - 8) and this is beyond the absolute limit of validity of the crack growth data obtained by the potential drop technique. Broadly similar trends to those observed at R = 0.1 have also been observed at R = 0.5, and these are considered elsewhere [10].

Generally, single dominant mode I cracks are observed to grow through the monolithic cladding layer (fig 4). This growth mechanism does not extend into the composite region. Several modes of damage have been observed in this region, and in many cases more than one of these modes of damage is observed. Mode I crack have been observed in some cases (fig 5) In one case more than one mode I crack appears to have grown (see fig 5). There have also been examples of the fibre bridging of these mode I cracks in a way similar to that observed in uniformly reinforced composites [4 - 7].

Delamination along the fibre mats is apparent in most specimens (fig 4 and fig 6). This is frequently along the first row of fibres (fig 6 and fig 7), but it may also feature in lower rows of fibres after subsequent crack bifurcation (fig 4 and fig 8). It is important to note that the fatigue damage in the fibre reinforced region tends to become distributed over a large volume of material. This is not generally seen in unclad uniformly reinforced composites, where single dominant mode I cracks are often observed. Fibres often bridge these cracks in uniformly reinforced material, reducing the effective ΔK at the crack tip, and hence reducing crack growth rates [4 - 7]. It should however be noted that most work on unclad composites has been carried out in orientations such that the crack growth direction was down fibre mats, whereas in the present case the crack growth direction is in the mat stacking direction. This wide distribution of damage throughout the composite region, in these selectively reinforced materials might suggest that the fatigue life of a selectively reinforced material might exceed that of the unreinforced matrix material, provided that transverse failure is not problematical.

These features have been observed in materials reinforced with both 15.9 and 31% volume fraction of fibres. Observations of these tests appear to indicate that delamination along fibre mats is more prevalent in the material containing 31% fibres, whereas in that containing 15.9% fibres, mode I type cracks and fibre bridging seem to be more likely to occur. The interfacial bond between the fibres and matrix is deliberately weak to facilitate fibre bridging. Thus the main resistance to delamination along fibre mats is due to the ligaments of titanium between the fibres. In a 2 mm wide test piece of the material reinforced with 15.9% fibres there are 8 fibres in a mat and hence a total of 1.2 mm of titanium. Compare this with a 2 mm wide section of the material with 31% fibres, in which there are 11 fibres in a mat and hence only 0.9 mm of titanium. Hence there is less resistance to delamination along fibre mats in the material containing 31% SiC fibres. It is, therefore plausible that in the material reinforced with 15.9% volume fraction of fibres, there is a greater resistance to delamination and thus other forms of damage, such as mode I cracks are more likely.

CONCLUSIONS

Fatigue crack growth in titanium MMCs reinforced selectively with 15.9 and 31.0% volume fractions of SiC fibres has been studied. Attention has been focused on the behaviour of fatigue cracks growing in monolithic cladding layers towards the reinforced regions. Tensile residual stresses exist in the cladding regions and the level of residual stress parallel to the fibres increases from 118 to 149 MPa as the volume fraction increases from 15.9 to 31.0%. Mode I fatigue cracks grow from single edged notches in the cladding layers, and eventually they interact with reinforced regions. Crack growth rates in the cladding layers are slightly faster than those observed for similar monolithic alloys at a low stress ratio, $R = 0.1$, and are consistent with the influence of residual stress in increasing the effective stress ratio. However, crack growth rates within the cladding layers appear to be similar for both volume fractions of reinforcement studied here. In the composite regions fatigue damage becomes widespread over a large volume of material. Mode I type cracks are observed, but cracks are also seen to bifurcate and delamination along fibre mats is often observed. Such arguments naturally promote great interest in the assessment of composite transverse properties as a function of volume fraction.

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Figure 1. Cross-section of a 15.9% volume fraction test piece

Figure 3. Crack growth resistance curves; da/dN versus applied ΔK for $R = 0.1$, 15.9% and 31% Ti-6-4 composite and monolithic Ti-6-4.

Figure 2. Plot showing residual stresses parallel to the fibre direction versus Z, hole depth in 15.9 and 31% volume fraction Ti-6Al-4V MMCs.

Figure 4. Secondary electron (SE) micrograph showing fatigue cracks in a 15.9% V_f testpiece, fatigued for 393,300 cycles at a R ratio of 0.5.

Figure 5. Fracture surface and Mode I fatigue cracks in a 15.9% V_f testpiece which failed after 293,550 cycles using a R ratio of 0.5 (photo side on)

Figure 6. Optical micrograph showing delamination along the first row of fibres in a 31% V_f testpiece, fatigued for 75,532 cycles using an R ratio of 0.1

Figure 7. Delamination along the first fibre mat in a 15.9% V_f testpiece (as in figure 5)

Figure 8. Crack bridging, bifurcation and delamination in a 15.9% V_f testpiece

PROCESSING AND WEAR PROPERTIES OF A (W,Ti)C PARTICULATE REINFORCED FERROUS-BASED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE.

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ABSTRACT

A particulate reinforced ferrous-based MMC has been developed which exhibits both excellent wear and cutting performance whilst achieving significant cost reductions over existing materials used in heavy wear applications.

A series of (W,Ti)C ferrous-based composite materials have been produced by direct addition of an innovative reinforcement powder, made by a self-propagating high-temperature synthesis reaction (SHS). This paper presents a study of how various process parameters influence the production of such composites. It also reports the unlubricated wear properties of materials as measured in a unidirectional pin-on-disc apparatus.

INTRODUCTION

It is well established that the incorporation of particulate carbides into ferrous matrices can significantly improve wear resistance properties [1,2,3]. However, conventional production routes used to fabricate these composite materials are usually energy and capital intensive and prove difficult to scale up to industrial size operations.

Self-propagating high-temperature synthesis provides an economical and energy efficient process route for the preparation of various hard ceramic particles which can be subsequently incorporated in a metallic matrix[4]. The SHS process typically involves mixing and compressing constituent elemental powders into a "green compact" then initiating an exothermic reaction by means of either a localised high voltage spark (combustion mode synthesis) or by heating the compact in a furnace (thermal explosion mode synthesis). This allows the propagation of a combustion wave which spreads through the compact. As the combustion wave advances, the reactants are converted to the final product material[5].

An innovative reinforcement material, which can be directly added to ferrous melts to form a particulate reinforced composite, has been produced by this SHS route. Iron-tungsten titanium carbide (Fe-WTiC) has been produced by the thermal explosion mode of synthesis

in a high frequency induction furnace. The resulting product consists of near spherical (W,Ti)C particles (1-10 μ m diameter) embedded in an iron matrix. The volume fraction of carbide can be varied from 50-85%. This Fe-WTiC, when added to a ferrous-based melt under carefully controlled conditions, disperses and forms a (W,Ti)C reinforced metal matrix composite.

The incorporation of the complex carbide (W,Ti)C into ferrous matrices is achieved by the direct addition of FeWTiC powder. This powder consists of individual carbides surrounded by a matrix of pure iron.

Fe-WTiC powder offers several interesting advantages over TiC powders produced by more conventional routes such as powder metallurgical and molten metal techniques, namely:-

- i) The SHS process, by its very nature, produces very high purity products due to the temperatures attained during the reaction[6]
- ii) The iron component of the powder leads to enhancement of carbide wetting characteristics when addition is made to ferrous melts, since the carbide is already wetted by the metal.
- iii) The tungsten component of the powder increases the carbide density and helps to prevent "floating out" of the carbide once it is incorporated into the melt.
- iv) The manufacture of these powders does not necessitate the use of intricate or difficult molten metal handling techniques or the use of specialised equipment.

The aim of this paper is to investigate the addition of Fe-WTiC powder to molten ferrous matrices to form a (W,Ti)C particulate reinforced composite. The effect that various process variables have on carbide dispersion and morphology will be explored. Wear resistance of these reinforced materials under unlubricated unidirectional sliding conditions will also be investigated and the possible wear mechanisms involved discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

COMPOSITE PRODUCTION

Specimens of composite material were processed by melting cast iron (3.4^{wt}%) and Fe-WTiC powder together in a high frequency induction furnace under both vacuum and in air. A volume fraction of 5.08% and 10.25% Fe-WTiC were "admixed" with the cast iron to give small specimens weighing 100g-150g. Average additive powder particle sizes were 2mm and 500 μ m, both of which had a nominal chemical composition as listed in table 1.

Table 1. Chemical analysis of Fe-WTiC powder

Element	C	Ti	W	Fe	O ₂	N ₂
wt%	10.46	37.67	33.75	14.77	1.45	0.56

After the molten iron engulfed the Fe-WTiC powder, the composite was held at a range of different temperatures, while continuously stirring by electromagnetic induction, for a

predesignated period of time. The material was cast into a chill mould located within the furnace chamber. The cast composite was then sectioned, ground and polished to a $1\mu\text{m}$ finish and examined using optical microscopy.

WEAR TESTING

A dedicated pin-on-disc apparatus was used for evaluating the sliding wear resistance of the (W,Ti)C reinforced composite materials. The discs were fabricated from a high Chromium cast iron ($\text{HV} \approx 1000$) with an average surface roughness, R_a , of $0.34\mu\text{m}$. The composite specimens, manufactured from cast composite material, were cylindrical in shape with a pin diameter of 0.006m . With the pin lowered onto the disc, a static weight was added via a balanced lever arm assembly. Normal forces in the range 10N to 100N were applied, corresponding to a nominal pressure of 0.354MPa to 3.890MPa respectively. The tests were performed in air at a relative humidity of $40\% \pm 5\%$ in accordance with National Physical Laboratories guidelines[7]. The rotational velocity was set using an optical tachometer at 1.5ms^{-1} . Tests were run over a sliding distance of $10,000\text{m}$. Two linear variable differential transformers (LVDT's) linked to a data logging system, were employed during the tests to measure pin displacement due to both pin and disc wear and also the coefficient of friction. A schematic of the pin-on-disc apparatus used is shown in Fig 1.

Figure 1. Schematic of pin-on-disc apparatus

The sliding wear resistance was evaluated on composites specimens containing 5% and 10% Fe-WTiC reinforcement, and for comparison, on iron alloy base material. The disc material was considerably harder than the composite pin material, thus minimising disc wear during the tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

COMPOSITE PRODUCTION

A photomicrograph of a specimen produced in air by mixing Fe-WTiC powder of average size $2\mu\text{m}$ at 1400°C in Fe- $3.4\text{wt}\%$ C, at a nominal volume fraction of 5.08% ($5\text{wt}\%$) is shown in Fig 2. This microstructure illustrates the problems associated with admixing large particles in an uncontrolled atmosphere. The majority of the Fe-WTiC powder remains undispersed in the melt or is rejected and floats to the surface. The lack of dispersion observed in this sample is due, in the main, to two factors: poor wetting and infiltration of the powder by the molten iron and to the large amount of porosity present in this size of powder. It is known that the

wettability of TiC by iron (the closest comparable system to (W,Ti)C is greatly affected by the nature of the surrounding atmosphere. Wettability is enhanced under inert gas conditions but is optimised under vacuum conditions (see table 2.)

Table 2. The wettability of TiC by liquid iron [8]

T (°C)	Atmosphere	Contact Angle(o)
1550	H ₂	49
1550	He	36
1490	vacuum	28

The large size of Fe-WTiC powder used also discourages wetting since less surface area is in contact with the molten iron.

When particle size is reduced but processing is still performed in air, then wettability and hence dispersion is significantly improved. However, carbide yields in composites processed in this way are low. Yields of less than 1^{wt}% carbide are common for a 5^{wt}% Fe-WTiC addition rate. This rejection of the carbides by the melt immediately after the molten iron has engulfed the powder has been attributed to the poor wettability of the carbides in air and the oxide layer which may exist around each Fe-WTiC powder particle.

It is known that the solubility of TiC in liquid iron decreases significantly with decreasing melt temperature [9]. Fig 3. shows photomicrographs of three specimens in which Fe-WTiC was added at a nominal volume fraction of 5.08%. They were held at 1300^o C, 1400^o C and 1500^o C for 10 minutes before being cast into the chill mould under vacuum. At a holding temperature of 1300^oC the microstructure consists of agglomerated, undispersed carbide powder ranging from 200µm to 20µm in size (individual (W,Ti)C particles in the Fe-WTiC matrix are in the order of 5µm). As the holding temperature is increased an improvement in the dispersion becomes evident, until at 1500^oC, full dispersion of the entire 5.08^{vol}% Fe-WTiC is achieved.

Figure 2. 2mm diameter Fe-WTiC powder in iron, held at 1400^oC for 20 minutes: magnification ×50

Figure 3. 5.08 vol% Fe-WTiC held at a) 1300°C b) 1400°C and c) 1500°C for 10 minutes: magnifications - a) $\times 50$ b) and c) $\times 400$

Titanium and carbon in solution significantly enhances the wetting characteristics and subsequent dispersion of TiC in molten iron.[2]. The dispersion of the complex carbide (W,Ti)C has been shown to be similarly affected by these elements in solution. At 1300°C, only a small amount of (W,Ti)C dissolution will occur, with the majority of the carbide remaining undissolved in the melt. The amount of Ti and C taken into solution at this temperature is insufficient to enhance the wetting characteristics of the majority of undissolved carbides. As the temperature is increased more Ti and C can be taken into solution by the dissolution of (W,Ti)C and enhanced wetting and dispersion of the remaining undissolved carbides occurs. By 1500°C, we have a larger amount of Ti and C dissolved in the melt; enough to fully disperse the full 5 vol % Fe-WTiC addition.

The enhanced wetting characteristics of (W,Ti)C by dissolved Ti and C is further demonstrated if we consider two further addition FeWTiC addition levels. For instance, a 10^{wt} % Fe-WTiC sample held at 1450°C exhibits a microstructure in which the carbide particles are not fully dispersed. It is only when a temperature of 1550°C is attained that sufficient Ti and C is dissolved to facilitate a fully dispersed sample.). At 1300°C, however, the small amount of dissolution that takes place is adequate to fully disperse an addition level of 2% Fe-WTiC.

It may be concluded that a dispersion of (W,Ti)C in iron, to form a particulate reinforced MMC, can be achieved by controlling 1) the atmosphere 2) the volume fraction and powder size of the addition and 3) the holding temperature of the melt, which controls the extent of carbide dissolution.

SLIDING WEAR RESISTANCE

Mild wear may be classed as any wear process which causes the loss of material by oxidation. It is characterised by finely divided wear debris which is predominantly an oxide. The worn surface is usually relatively smooth. Severe wear, in contrast, results in much larger particles of metallic debris and a correspondingly roughened surface. The sliding wear of most metals

and alloys in air is generally associated with a period of relatively severe wear, followed by a transition to a period of mild wear, the transition being related to the generation of sufficient oxide to limit metal-metal interactions.

Measurements of sliding wear rates (mm^3m^{-1}) against load (N) exhibited by specimens containing 0^{wt%}, 5^{wt%}, and 10^{wt%} Fe-WTiC are reported in Fig 4. It is clear from these results that the Fe-WTiC reinforced materials behave differently from the untreated alloy, especially at loads greater than 60N (equivalent to a stress of 2.1MPa). Over the entire loading range, the reinforced alloys consistently exhibit a lower wear rate, with the 10^{wt%} Fe-WTiC specimen showing best wear resistance. The untreated alloy demonstrates a marked transition at around 70N from mild to severe wear. In contrast, the 10^{wt%} Fe-WTiC reinforced alloy exhibits mild wear characteristics over the entire loading range investigated, with no wear mechanism transitions apparent. The alloy containing 5^{wt%} Fe-WTiC undergoes a less severe, but nevertheless significant, transition at around 60N to an increased rate of wear. Tests performed at loads of 60N and above at this addition level were characterised by an extended period of severe wear at the start of the test and then a transition to mild wear which continued for the remainder of the test. The wear rates plotted for the 5% reinforced alloy at 60N and above in figure 4, have been calculated from both mild and severe wear rate data.

Figure 4. Wear rate v 's load for specimens containing 0%, 5%, and 10% Fe-WTiC

The coefficient of friction for tests loaded at 30N at the 10^{wt%} addition level and on unreinforced material are illustrated in figure 5. At 30N, where both materials exhibit mild wear, it can be seen that the coefficient of friction of the reinforced material is significantly higher than that of the unreinforced. This is especially notable at the start of the test where the generation of a cohesive oxide layer is particularly important if prevention of metal-metal contact and its associated high wear rate is to be avoided. The higher coefficients of friction observed when reinforcing particles are present in the alloys is typical across the range of loads used in these tests. A higher coefficient of friction can be directly correlated with the local generation of heat which, in turn, significantly affects the oxidational behaviour of the wear couple involved. The (W,Ti)C particulates present in these alloys increase the frictional force at the wear interface which leads to oxide films being established much more rapidly. This effect is most obvious in the 10^{wt%} reinforced alloy where an oxide film is established quickly enough at the start of the test to almost prevent the brief period of severe wear which

occurs prior to mild wear. The oxide film formed is discontinuous and protruding carbide particles keep friction and heat high throughout the duration of the test. Even if the mechanism operating is an "oxidation-scrape-reoxidation" process [10], the reoxidation rate of the reinforced alloy will be greater, thus leading to reduced wear rate

Figure 5. The coefficient of Friction at 30N load for a) unreinforced alloy and b) 10^{wt%} reinforced alloy.

At higher loads a similar wear mechanism operates. In the material reinforced with 10^{wt%} Fe-WTiC oxides are generated quickly enough to prevent severe wear for all but the briefest of periods at the start of the test. The 5^{wt%} sample undergoes an extended period of severe wear (characterised by the creation of metallic debris) before the frictional heat associated with the reinforcement eventually establishes a stable enough oxide to prevent further severe wear and a transition to mild wear is observed. Unreinforced base alloy undergoes no such transition and wears by severe wear throughout the duration of the test.

Finally, it should be noted that the oxidation wear of metals is a complex process and many factors may exert an influence on wear behaviour. The incorporation of reinforcing particulates into the system is yet another variable which further complicates the situation. The load bearing capacity of the particulates and their effect on the material's thermal conductivity etc. have not been considered in this paper.

CONCLUSIONS

- 1) The microstructure of composites produced by dispersing (W,Ti)C particles in cast iron can be controlled by controlling the volume fraction and size of Fe-WTiC powder added, holding temperature and time, and atmosphere.
- 2) Wear experiments over a wide range of applied loads, using a pin-on-disc machine, showed that the addition of (W,Ti)C considerably improves the wear properties of iron-based alloys.
- 3) A sharp transition from mild to severe wear was observed with increasing load in the base alloy, but not in material containing 10^{wt%} FeWTiC. At this addition level, mild wear is observed over the full range of loading. At any given load above 60N, material containing 5^{wt%} Fe-WTiC undergoes a transition from an extended period of severe wear to mild wear for the remainder of the test. It is proposed that an increase in the coefficient of friction associated with the addition of (W,Ti)C reinforcement is responsible for these wear mechanisms.

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